

Bodies Outside the Gender Binary: Transitivity Analysis of Intersex News in Thai Newspapers

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Abstract

Thai newspapers limit the recognition of intersex autonomy. They often portray intersex bodies as obstacles to the expression of naturalized masculine and feminine identities. This study analyzes how Thai newspaper clauses representing intersex individuals contribute to meaning-making within a Systemic Functional Grammar perspective. The study assumes that intersex bodies are consistently depicted as sites of gender performativity and serve as focal points for broader societal debates about the “real” sex and gender. Data were collected from online news articles published between 2012 and 2023 by seven Thai news agencies: BBC Thai, Daily News, Ejan, Khaosod, Matichon, MGR Online, and Thairath. A total of 36 articles were examined. The findings show that intersex voices predominantly appear in mental and relational clauses. These clauses construct experiential meanings that encode categorical relationships between intersex individuals and atypical conditions, framing them as matters of medical necessity. Thai newspapers frequently invoke authoritative medical voices to reinforce the perceived need for medical intervention, particularly in the case of intersex children. These medical voices mainly occur in verbal and material clauses, where they interact with the voices of parents, government agencies, and charity officers to legitimize appeals for “sex-normalizing” procedures. Government voices foreground social constraints through behavioral clauses, reinforcing the alienation experienced by intersex children. This study argues that Thai newspapers align biological sex with the gender binary, thereby perpetuating the perceived naturalness of masculine and feminine identities. Variations in sex development, especially among children, are framed as urgent problems that require intervention to conform to socially accepted gender norms.

Keywords

Bodies, gender binary, transitivity analysis, intersex, Thai newspapers

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Introduction

In Thai society, the binary classification of male and female, determined at birth, is considered natural. The term “phet” in Thai integrates multiple dimensions, including sex characteristics, gender expression, and sexual desire. To clarify the social and cultural distinctions within these concepts, Thai scholars and activists have introduced three terms: “phetsarira” (sex), “phetsathana” (gender), and “phetwithi” (sexuality). Gender politics extensively engages with “phetsathana” and “phetwithi,” while “phetsarira” is often discussed separately because scholars consider biological sex innate rather than a socially constructed category. Scholars frequently define biological sex through biomedical criteria, drawing on chromosomal, hormonal, and anatomical markers (Komutee, 2020; Rangnoy, 2023). Building on this reasoning, the male-female classification is justified by reproductive capability (Mangkud, 2021). This understanding reinforces the belief that sex exists independently of social and cultural influences, leading to the categorization of individuals with variations in sex development as having disorders.

However, the existence of intersex variations in Thai society remains largely unknown. Preliminary evidence from a pilot study suggests that, in the current Thai social context, there is no widely accepted term to refer to intersex conditions that aligns with the definitions advocated by international activist movements. When discussing intersex, the transliterated term “intersex” is used. Historical records related to sexual knowledge suggest that the term intersex is conceptually similar to the Thai word “kathoei.” However, it is crucial to note that the term “kathoei” has undergone significant semantic and contextual changes over time. Historically, “kathoei” referred to individuals or beings that were neither male nor female but possessed only a urinary opening. It was sometimes used to describe individuals with ambiguous genitalia, rendering their sex indeterminable (Samanchan, 2024). After 1804, Thai society began using the term “kathoei” to describe individuals who exhibited gender expressions contrary to their assigned male or female sex at birth. At this point, societal perceptions of “kathoei” diverged into two distinct categories: physical kathoei, which closely aligns with the modern understanding of intersex, and social kathoei, encompassing identities such as “ladyboys” and “tomboys” (Thongkrajai, 2023). Over time, the concept of physical kathoei gradually faded from public awareness, leaving only its social dimension, which became associated with gender expression and sexuality diverging from one’s assigned sex at birth. Notably, historical records have never documented the gender self-perceptions voiced by individuals socially referred to as kathoei. Consequently, there is no insight into how these individuals genuinely perceive their own bodies and gender identities.

When social issues concerning intersex individuals first surfaced in Thai public discourse, many Thais expressed disbelief and questioned whether bodies that are neither male nor female could exist. The emergence of intersex debates in Thailand was not initiated by activists but triggered by the controversy over Imane Khelif, an Algerian boxer whose “true sex” was contested after her victory at the 2024 Olympics. Between August and early October 2024, Thai newspapers and social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter (X) became arenas for competing voices. A large number of public commentators sought to “expose” Imane Khelif’s real sex in order to argue that she possessed unfair advantages in competitive sports. These debates were saturated with transphobic attitudes

and revealed the widespread inability to distinguish intersex from transgender identities. Some online articles attempted to explain that Imane Khelif displayed anatomical traits associated with intersex conditions, but skepticism persisted among Thai social media users. A small group of intersex activists, drawing on Western activist perspectives, sought to frame Khelif’s body as reflecting intersex variations. Their claims, however, were widely dismissed as “wokeness.” This rejection rested on an essentialist belief that “true sex” is fixed by chromosomal evidence (XX or XY) or by reproductive organs such as the uterus or testes.

Many in Thai society reject the existence of intersex as part of sexual diversity because the conceptualization of sexual diversity in Thailand excludes variations in physical sex characteristics. Instead, it focuses solely on diversity in gender expression and sexual behavior. A review of Thai newspaper coverage reveals that intersex has been framed primarily as a peculiar medical condition. Thai newspapers frequently depict intersex individuals with limited acknowledgment of their bodily autonomy, portraying their genital structures as anomalies necessitating urgent medical intervention. Such representations serve dual purposes: to inform readers about rare medical conditions and to evoke pity by emphasizing perceived abnormalities, thereby arousing public curiosity. This sensationalist tone is evident in headlines such as “Defusing the Drama: Kathoey Disease in Medical Terms Does Not Refer to LGBT” (Thairath-04) and “Shocking: Girl Grows Male Genitalia - A Rare Case of Two Sexes in One Person” (Khaosod-03). These portrayals highlight the tendency of Thai newspapers to reject the concept of biological sex beyond the male-female binary.

In contrast, international discourses on intersex have progressed through debates and social movements, reframing intersex as a form of biological variation that fosters the development of a distinct identity rather than viewing it as a disorder. The Organization Intersex International (OII) defines intersex as encompassing variations in sex development, including individuals whose chromosomal, gonadal, endocrine, or anatomical traits deviate from societal expectations of male and female bodies (Mestre, 2022). The term “intersex” has shifted away from its medicalized origins, now affirming bodily diversity and challenging normative sex-gender systems (Amato, 2016; Holms, 2009). Bastien-Charlebois (2016) highlights systemic injustices faced by intersex individuals, such as barriers to forming political identities and achieving societal recognition.

These shifts in discourse contest binary gender norms and advocate for broader recognition of intersex experiences. Media in Europe and the United States provides a more nuanced understanding of intersex issues, focusing on ethical debates surrounding gender-affirming treatments and the political implications of intersex identity (Carpenter, 2021; Hegarty et al., 2021). In contrast, Thai media rarely engages with these topics. Instead, it portrays intersex individuals as struggling to access gender-affirming surgeries, often depicting intersex children as having multiple disabilities. Terms like “phet kamkuam” (ambiguous genitalia), “khon song phet” (bi-genital person), and “rok kathoey” (kathoey disease) are frequently used. These terms associate intersex bodies with social deviance and illness, reinforcing deviations from the sex binary. Consequently, Thai media’s framing of intersex issues diverges significantly from the perspectives advanced by international intersex movements.

The portrayal of intersex lives in the media significantly shapes public perceptions. Language is fundamental in constructing how we understand the world. Halliday and Matthiessen (2014) argue that language constructs “experiential meaning” by representing reality through processes, participant roles, and circumstances within clauses. The emergence of intersex issues in public discourse, particularly in Thai newspapers, and their linguistic dimensions lead to two research questions: how intersex bodies are portrayed and what linguistic devices are used to convey knowledge about intersex individuals.

These research questions examine the hypothesis that Thai newspapers construct intersex understandings through medical discourse, which is closely aligned with binary gender discourse. As a result, intersex individuals are positioned within a medicalized discourse of abnormality and discursively separated from the sphere of sexual diversity. The linguistic resources used to represent intersex characteristics reinforce medical perspectives and highlight the assumed alignment of the gender binary with biological sex. The findings aim to contribute to social analysis through a linguistic lens and to inform policy recommendations for broadening the understanding of intersex variations. This study advocates recognition of intersex individuals’ right to full bodily autonomy and supports framing intersex diversity as an integral dimension of biological variation.

1. Literature review

1.1. Embodiment, language, and Gendered Bodies

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Human physical embodiment is shaped and understood through discourse (Butler, 1993). Discourse enables conceptualizing corporeality, allowing relational practices to be articulated and defined. Discourse and the body are inextricably linked in a complex, recursive, and co-constructed relationship (King, 2016). These patterns of reasoning shift across time, place, and interpersonal relationships. Consequently, understandings of the human body derive meaning not from a natural order that pre-exists in language but from discourse itself. The body is where gender matters circulate repeatedly (Bucholtz and Hall, 2006). Bodies are neither neutral anatomical structures nor static biological systems; instead, they are imbued with categorical meanings shaped by intersecting biological, social, and cultural narratives. For instance, body parts are gendered through meanings such as male or female sex characteristics, masculine traits, or feminine voices, which emerge through a dynamic interplay between scientific knowledge and societal constructs. These categorical meanings, though culturally contingent, regulate the perception of bodies within social systems. They influence how individuals navigate their sense of self and engage with societal norms. Moreover, while gendered meanings lack intrinsic ties to biological traits, they remain powerful tools in perpetuating normative discourses about identity and embodiment.

Language is a systemic resource for transmitting practices tied to gendered bodies. This transmission occurs through linguistic features such as speech acts, indexicality, hedges, tag questions, rising intonation, politeness markers, and silence (Gal, 1995; Lakoff, 1975; Silverstein, 1976). These linguistic practices gain their significance through

interpretation in alignment with gender norms, which are shaped by shared assumptions and repeated social practices. Shared knowledge guides individuals in interpreting these norms, producing discursive patterns of gendered behavior. For instance, Secomb (2017) demonstrates how presupposed shared knowledge reinforces the connection between gender and the body. Physical actions such as gestures, postures, and movements are not merely functional; they carry embedded social meanings. A woman’s cross-legged posture may signify modesty, while manspreading, in which men sit with legs apart in public spaces, projects rugged masculinity and reinforces socially constructed gender norms. In this way, gendered meanings are not inherent to human nature but are socially constructed, emerging through the interplay of linguistic practices and shared knowledge, which shape how individuals enact gender in their social interactions.

The pilot study raises a crucial question about intersex bodies in Thai discourse. In mainstream narratives, the body is seen as inherently linked to gender through a natural systemic relationship, often supported by biomedical evidence. However, intersex bodies, despite biological evidence of divergence from male and female norms, are rendered unintelligible and seen as obstacles to achieving “real” gender consciousness. This exclusion prompts a key inquiry: why are intersex bodies denied recognition and agency in the body-gender relationship? This study argues that understandings of the body emerge through public discourse. How bodies are discussed shapes subjective experiences and perceptions, showing that language is not just a tool for communication but a constitutive force defining how individuals perceive their embodiment in the social world.

1.2. Transitivity

Transitivity, within the framework of Systemic Functional Linguistics (Halliday and Matthiessen, 2014), refers to a grammatical system that encodes experiential meanings. This system encompasses our interactions with the material world, inner consciousness, and symbolic representation. These experiential meanings are realized through processes (verbs) that signify actions, events, or states. The processes include obligatory elements to complete their meaning, namely participants, which refer to entities directly involved in the processes, while circumstances provide additional details such as time, space, cause, manner, or other contextual factors. For example, in the clause “[Location:] in the open glade [Actor:] the wild rabbits [Process:] danced [Accompaniment:] with their shadows,” each element contributes to constructing an experiential meaning of the activity.

This study applies transitivity analysis to examine how Thai newspapers represent intersex individuals through the lexicogrammar that construes experiential meanings. It focuses on how language contributes to shaping societal norms around the gender binary. By examining process types and participant roles, the study links transitivity patterns to the distinctive features of the Thai language (see Table 1).

Table 1. Types of processes, participants, and circumstances (Adapted from Eggins, 2004; Thompson, 2014)

No.	Participants	Processes	Participants	Circumstances
1	Actor	Material (Make, Destroy)	Goal, Scope, Recipient, Attribute	Extent Location Manner Cause Contingency Accompaniment Role Matter Angle
2	Behaver	Behavioral (Watch, Laugh)		
3	Senser	Mental (Think, Believe)	Phenomenon, Inducer	
4	Sayer	Verbal (Say, Announce)	Receiver, Verbiage, Target	
5	Identified	Relational process (Be, Have)	Identifier	
	Carrier		Attribute	
6	Existent	Existential (Exist, Remain)		

1.3. Intersex in public discourse

The term intersex first appeared in the Thai social context in 2021, introduced by activist groups. These activists adopted the definition of intersex from Western movements and integrated it with pre-existing perspectives on sexual diversity in Thai society. In this context, intersex refers to individuals whose physical characteristics do not conform clearly to male or female categories. Intersex traits manifest in diverse forms, stemming from complex variations in chromosomes, hormones, and internal and external reproductive structures.

However, due to laws, medical practices, and societal norms rooted in a binary gender system, many intersex individuals are compelled to choose between identifying as either male or female. This choice often leads to processes of gender normalization from childhood through institutions such as family and education. An examination of intersex discourse articulated by intersex activists in Thailand reveals a critical engagement with mainstream narratives. These activists challenge the societal stigma that frames intersex as a disorder, arguing instead that intersex represents a form of biological diversity. They assert that intersex individuals serve as evidence that the binary gender system is a socially constructed “myth.”

Public discourse on intersex in Thai media is notably fragmented. The first portrayal of an intersex individual on Thai television occurred in 2005 on the program *Tee Sip Day*. In this context, the existence of intersex was not acknowledged, nor was there any specific terminology used to describe this complex sexual variation. The program presented the story of an individual described as “neither fully a woman, nor entirely a man, nor accepted as a transgender person,” with a body deemed perplexing. The segment aimed not to educate the audience about intersex but to highlight the subject’s unusualness, invoking pity as a means to solicit help.

In contrast, media content produced by medical institutions classifies intersex under the category of ambiguous genital disorders. Medical narratives emphasize clinical descriptions, diagnostic guidelines, and treatment approaches. Meanwhile, Thai newspapers report on intersex individuals by simultaneously emphasizing their perceived oddity and evoking sympathy, often to solicit donations. These publications frequently use terms such as “bi-genital person,” “ambiguous sex,” “bizarre disease,” or “ambiguous genital disorder” to refer to intersex individuals. Alarming, public media produced by activist groups receives minimal exposure and appears largely unknown to the wider public. Consequently, the voices of intersex individuals who affirm their existence remain significantly marginalized within the Thai social context.

A review of intersex research in Thailand reveals significant gaps. First, fewer than eight studies address intersex issues, and these are limited to the fields of medicine, law, and religion. Second, all existing research reinforces the perception of intersex as a disorder across various dimensions, emphasizing the necessity of medical intervention.

Medical research primarily focuses on screening methods for intersex conditions, treatment guidelines, and monitoring the development of masculine or feminine identities following sex reassignment surgery (Kirdchok et al., 2017; Nakprasit et al., 2021). Legal studies propose extending the ethical regulation period for gender-affirming surgeries, lowering the age of consent for such procedures from 18 to 16 to align gender identity with sex reassignment surgery and hormone therapy (Yooman, 2016), and amending laws to protect intersex individuals from discrimination. These proposals advocate granting intersex individuals rights comparable to those of persons with disabilities, citing physical differences such as ambiguous genitalia and hormonal variations as justification (Watcharasakaowong and Muangtham, 2024).

Religious studies explore intersex through a Buddhist lens, arguing that the concept of intersex is not new to Thai society but has been addressed in religious interpretations. Mahanarongchai and Chatsuwana (2024) classify intersex individuals under the Buddhist category of “Pandaka” (hermaphrodites), divided into two types: “Opakkamiyapandaka,” referring to individuals with dual-sex characteristics, believed to result from past karma and capable of performing both male and female sexual functions; and “Napunsakapandaka,” referring to individuals with no visible genitalia or ambiguous genitalia, making gender categorization impossible. Both types are regarded as physically deficient, dominated by lustful desires, and deemed incapable of attaining enlightenment or ordination as monks within Buddhist doctrine.

Conversely, Sirisakko (2023) challenges this view, asserting that Pandaka individuals can achieve enlightenment, akin to males and females, despite their perceived sexual abnormalities. This argument insists that spiritual attainment is contingent on individual mental states rather than physical conditions. Sirisakko further contends that the exclusion of Pandaka from religious ordination stems from specific Theravada interpretations of the Tripitaka, rather than reflecting an intrinsic Buddhist principle.

International research shows that media shapes public perceptions of intersex individuals. Studies indicate that public media often reinforces treatment approaches aligned with

gender binary norms. Kerry (2011) noted that Australian media coverage of intersex individuals, such as the murder suspect Kathleen Worrall, focused on mood disorders linked to intersex traits like congenital adrenal hyperplasia. Such reporting engages in dialogue with medical and psychological discourses to associate intersex individuals with mental disorders. Lane (2018), using a Queer Feminist Science Studies lens to analyze U.S. media, found that coverage of M.C. Crawford often emphasized medical errors as causes of “gender identity confusion.” Media rarely criticized invasive procedures on intersex children. Reports usually suggested that failed gender assignments in intersex children resulted from inadequate access to white-standard medical care. Funk et al. (2019) concluded that media narratives rarely supported the development of intersex identity and instead promoted “correction” through irreversible medical interventions.

Research on intersex individuals in Thai society remains limited, particularly regarding language use and media representations. Existing discourse predominantly construes intersex traits within a rigid binary gender system, marginalizing voices that affirm intersex identities as expressions of biological diversity. These gaps raise critical questions about the current understanding of intersex issues and the perspectives of Thai newspapers toward intersex individuals. This study seeks to investigate whether Thai media paradigms are shifting in addressing these issues, while also examining how language and media shape societal perceptions of intersex individuals in Thailand.

2. Methodology and data collection

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This study employs a qualitative methodology, using textual analysis to explore how Thai newspapers depict the bodies and experiences of intersex individuals. Data were collected from online news articles published from 2012 to 2023 by seven Thai news agencies: BBC Thai, Daily News, Ejan, Khaosod, Matichon, MGR Online, and Thairath. A total of 36 articles were examined.

News about intersex individuals in Thailand was collected using key terms identified from the pilot study: “khon song phet” (bi-genital person), “phet kamkuam” (ambiguous genitalia), “chak chai pen ying” (from male to female), “rok kathoey” (kathoey disease), and “in tœ sek” (intersex). Clause structures and verb-dependent elements from headlines, leads, and news bodies were examined to explore meanings conveyed in clauses. This approach offers insights into how newspapers depict the lives of intersex individuals. Linguistic evidence was interpreted through the lens of gender as a concept repeatedly enacted through intersex bodies. The anonymity of intersex individuals and their families is preserved throughout this article. All analytical data are marked with abbreviations, detailed in Table 2.

Table 2. List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition	Abbreviation	Definition
ACT	Actor	MATT	Matter
ANG	Angle	MAT	Material
ATT	Attribute	MENT	Mental
BEH	Behaver	PHEN	Phenomenon
BEHAV	Behavioral	RECV	Receiver
CAR	Carrier	RECP	Recipient
EXT	Extent	REL	Relational
GOL	Goal	SAY	Sayer
IDED	Identified	SEN	Senser
IDR	Identifier	TAR	Target
LOC	Location	VER	Verbal
MAN	Manner	VERB	Verbiage

3. Results

Experiential meanings in Thai newspapers depict intersex bodies through six characteristics: “strange bodies,” “miserable bodies,” “ambiguous bodies,” “medically gazed bodies,” “abnormal bodies,” and “socially problematic bodies.” These representations rely on five processes: material, behavioral, mental, verbal, and relational. These processes not only describe intersex bodies but also reinforce social norms emphasizing alignment between biological sex and the gender binary. Newspapers commonly use the term “phet kamkuan” (ambiguous genitalia), reflecting medical terminology to describe physical conditions. Coverage of advocacy for intersex rights is notably absent, with reports focusing solely on medical treatment, misery, and strangeness.

3.1. Strange bodies

Variations in sex development among intersex individuals are not only excluded from the binary categories of male and female but are also classified as unusual traits. Newspapers represent intersex perspectives in ways that suggest intersex individuals might perceive their bodies in relation to typical male and female definitions. Relational clauses are used by intersex individuals to interpret these variations. The experiential meaning portrays these variations not as diversity but as factors leading to societal alienation. When reporting intersex voices, newspapers do not explore how intersex individuals perceive their bodies within the context of strangeness. Linguistic evidence shows that both intersex individuals and newspapers assume that typical sexual characteristics are binary. This shared assumption reinforces binary norms and further marginalizes intersex bodies.

- (1) rao^{CAR} **du plaek pralat**^{REL}
(I look strange.) (Khaosod-02)
(2) phom^{IDED} **pen**^{REL} tua pralat^{IDR}
(I am a freak.) (BBC Thai-01)

In example (1), the relational clause uses the process “du plaek pralat” (look strange) to express the attribute perceived through visual perception of the carrier, “rao” (I). Here, the carrier refers to an intersex individual embodying the attribute of strangeness. In Thai, “plaek pralat” can also function as a verb in a serial verb construction. While “rao” is often a collective pronoun, in this case, it serves as a first-person singular pronoun. Its referentiality excludes the listener and evokes a sense of detachment between the speaker (the carrier) and the attribute. The relational clause reflects the intersex individual’s observation of variations in their sex development, leading to a subjective interpretation of strangeness. This interpretation is influenced by socio-cultural knowledge distinguishing typical from atypical sex development.

In example (2), the relational clause involves an identifying relational process. The process “pen” (am) establishes a categorical relationship between the identified “phom” (I) in the subject position and the identifier “tua pralat” (freak) in the complement position. This relational process categorizes the intersex individual under the label of “freak.”

When newspapers depict the strangeness of intersex bodies in their voice, they employ relational clauses to convey meanings that reinforce a perceived detachment between intersex individuals and the concept of ordinary people. This “detachment” reflects a categorization that separates the unusual from the normal.

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- (3) khon lao ni^{IDED} **mai muean**^{REL} khon thammada thuapai^{IDR}
(These people are not like ordinary people.) (MGR online-04)

The relational clause in example (3) establishes a relationship between “khon lao ni” (these people) in the subject position and “khon thammada thuapai” (ordinary people) in the complement position. However, the relational process “muean” (like) is negated by “mai” (not), creating an opposite meaning. This implies that “khon lao ni” does not belong to the category of “khon thammada thuapai.” In this context, “khon lao ni” refers to intersex individuals, while “khon thammada thuapai” represents males and females in society. The negation of the relational process emphasizes the exclusion of intersex individuals from normative male and female categories. This exclusion reflects a societal tendency to marginalize those who do not conform to the gender binary system. The use of the negated relational process reinforces the perceived strangeness or otherness of intersex bodies, further entrenching gender binary norms and positioning intersex individuals outside those boundaries.

The relational clauses in these constructions convey a specific event that excludes intersex individuals from societal norms. Beyond distinguishing intersex individuals from the categories of male and female, newspapers also emphasize the voices of intersex individuals to reinforce the notion that many within this group share similar perceptions of their bodies.

3.2. Miserable bodies

Newspapers commonly employ descriptions of external genitalia that deviate from male or female classifications to evoke feelings of misery, particularly in cases involving intersex children from financially disadvantaged families. Newspapers not only use their own voice to solicit help for intersex individuals but also engage in dialogue with the voices of intersex children’s parents in these appeals. These efforts emphasize the urgent need for medical intervention. Intersex variations are portrayed as additional burdens on the lives of intersex individuals, reinforcing the perception of their struggle due to nonconformity with the gender binary. Newspapers convey this experiential meaning through verbal and mental clauses, with verbal processes often directed toward groups of philanthropists.

(4) khonsongphet^{SAY} won^{VER} [phuchaibun^{RECV} chuai ok^{MAT} khachaichai^{GOL} nai kantat awaiyawaphet ying ok^{MATT}]^{VERB}

(The bi-genital person appeals to philanthropists for help covering the cost of surgery to remove female genitalia.) (MGR Online-02)

(5) (omitted)^{SAY} yak won kho^{VER} [hai phuchaibun^{RECV} yuen mu chuailua^{MAT} rueang khachaichai nai kanphatat^{MATT}]^{VERB}

(Appeal to philanthropists to extend a helping hand with the surgery expenses.) (MGR Online-03)

The verbal processes “won” and “yak won kho” (to appeal) in examples (4) and (5) are causative-verbal clauses consisting of projected clauses in the verbiage position. Rather than merely reporting statements, the newspaper integrates the voices of intersex individuals and parents into its narrative. In example (4), the verbal process projects an action from the intersex voice, referred to as “khon song phet” (bi-genital person). In example (5), the newspaper incorporates the mother’s voice by omitting the sayer in the subject position. These appeals articulate a dialogue that conveys pleas for help and encourages readers to respond, emphasizing that the supplicant cannot achieve the goal alone. These verbal processes consistently target “phuchaibun” (philanthropists), expecting them to act on behalf of the supplicant. The newspaper employs verbal clauses to request expenses related to surgical interventions. Such appeals establish a relationship between philanthropists and intersex individuals and imply the impoverished living conditions of intersex individuals, who can only reciprocate by acting as a bridge for merit-making.

The newspaper engages in dialogue with the mother’s perspective on her intersex child to evoke pity for living with variations in sex development. In example (6), a mental clause explicitly conveys pity toward the intersex child. This study found that the pity expressed in the news content arose not from concerns about the child’s illness but from anticipated social challenges in gender categorization.

(6) ton eng^{SEN} songsan^{MENT} luk^{PHEN}

(I myself feel pity for my child.) (Matichon-01)

The mental clause expresses a feeling of “songsan” (pity), with the senser “ton eng” (I myself) experiencing the emotion directed toward “luk” (my child) as the phenomenon. This clause depicts an event where emotional distress arises from witnessing another person’s suffering. According to the news, parents and doctors assigned a male gender to a 10-year-old intersex child, but the phalloplasty (male gender-affirming surgery) remains incomplete. The child requires further corrective surgeries to accommodate bodily changes and will undergo androgen therapy until the age of 16 to promote male characteristics. Due to the incomplete surgery, the child experiences pain during urination.

The newspaper does not explain the rationale for assigning a male gender or performing surgery before puberty, which involves multiple surgeries and hormone treatments over time. This reflects the perception that sex development outside the binary system constitutes an emergency requiring immediate intervention. Consequently, parents and doctors are portrayed as justified in making life-altering decisions on behalf of the child.

3.3. Ambiguous bodies

Thai newspapers report that many intersex individuals face challenges due to a mismatch between their gender identity and their birth-assigned sex, often resulting in gender dysphoria. The binary approach to sex assignment leads intersex individuals to feel that defining themselves strictly as a man or woman based solely on gender identity is inadequate. Newspapers convey this ambiguity through mental, verbal, and relational clauses. This linguistic evidence indicates that society recognizes “true” sex and gender only within a binary notion. Although ambiguous genitalia do not affect health, they complicate the classification of “true” sex because society ties biological sex to the identity of either man or woman.

(7) ton nan^{LOC} phom^{SEN} **sapson**^{MENT} pai mot^{MAN}
(At that time, I was completely confused.) (BBC Thai-01)

(8) rao^{SEN} **sapson**^{MENT} nai phet saphap tua eng^{MATT} [wa sarup laeo rao^{IDED} pen^{REL} phuying
rue phuchai^{IDR}] ^{PHEN}
(I am confused about my own gender identity, trying to conclude whether I am
a woman or a man.) (Thairath-03)

In examples (7) and (8), the newspaper conveys intersex voices expressing gender dysphoria through mental processes labeled “sapson” (confused). The sensors in the subject positions, “phom” (I) and “rao” (I), refer to intersex individuals perceiving these processes. In example (9), the mental clause projects an idea (phenomenon) using the complementizer “wa” (that), reporting the thought “sarup laeo rao pen phuying rue phuchai” (trying to conclude whether I am a woman or a man). This thought centers on the relational process “pen” (am), which establishes a categorical relationship within gender identity. The conjunction “rue” (or) marks a binary choice and underscores the limited options available. The experiential meaning of these mental clauses reflects an individual’s perception of an event where they struggle to understand a concept that remains unclear. This suggests that intersex variations do not align with male or female categories, creating internal conflict when the body does not conform to societal definitions of man or woman.

The newspaper dialogues with the medical voice to provide details about ambiguous genitalia and emphasizes urgency. Medical records classify ambiguous genitalia as a medical emergency due to difficulties in assigning sex within the binary system. It is viewed as both a medical and social crisis. In children, this condition causes parental concern, affecting their guidance under traditional gender expectations.

(9) nangsue raprong phaet^{SAY} **rabu**^{VER} [wa mi^{REL} awaiyawa suepphan kamkuam^{ATT}]^{VERB}
(The medical certificate states that the intersex individual has ambiguous reproductive organs.) (Thairath-02)

In example (9), the newspaper engages with the medical voice by presenting medical records as the sayers in the verbal clauses. The verbal process “rabu” (states) projects a locution (utterance) in the verbiage position. This projected clause imparts the relational process “mi” (has), assigning an attribute to the carrier. The attribute indicates that the intersex individual has ambiguous reproductive organs. Although the carrier in the subject position is not explicitly mentioned, contextual cues suggest that it refers to an intersex individual, as implied by the medical record in the sayer position.

In some cases, the newspaper does not explicitly mention ambiguous genitalia but implies it through verb-dependent elements, as in example (10). The relational process “mi” (had) assigns the attribute “awaiyawaphet chai lae ying yu tit kan” (male and female genitals next to each other) to the carrier “dek chai” (the boy). This attribute reflects the limits of language within the gender binary system, as the newspaper must reference both male and female genitalia to describe intersex characteristics. The experiential meaning suggests that intersex sex characteristics include both male and female elements developing simultaneously. This reinforces societal norms expecting alignment with one of two sexes and portrays the intersex body as ambiguous due to the mixture of characteristics from both sexes.

(10) dek chai^{CAR} **mi**^{REL} awaiyawaphet chai lae ying yu tit kan^{ATT}
(The boy had male and female genitals next to each other.) (MGR online-03)

In Thai, there are no specific terms for genitals outside male or female categories. As a result, newspapers use language that reinforces the gender binary system. Describing an intersex individual as having both male and female genitalia fails to acknowledge intersex variations and shows that mainstream media does not recognize the existence of intersex individuals. The experiential meanings in these clauses suggest that intersex genitals are perceived as anomalies due to the presence of “extra” genital parts. Newspapers do not rely solely on their voice to frame intersex characteristics as abnormalities but also draw upon multiple voices, including those of intersex individuals and medical perspectives, to reinforce the portrayal of ambiguous genitalia.

3.4. Medically gazed bodies

Newspapers report abnormalities in intersex bodies by engaging with medical voices, including urological surgeons, psychiatrists, and medical teams. References to medical

authorities reinforce the view that intersex individuals' sexual development results from a genetic disorder rather than anatomical diversity. Information from medical voices is treated as the sole truth, as both newspapers and much of the Thai public perceive biomedical knowledge as objective and reliable. Bodies that deviate from the gender binary are framed as abnormalities requiring treatment. Medical voices are predominantly cited through verbal clauses linked to the reporting of medical diagnoses.

(11) sanlayaphaet thangdoen patsawa^{SAY} **rabu**^{VER} [dek songphet wai sipsam pi^{ACT} thi Suphanburi^{LOC} tong phueng^{MAT} chittaphaet^{GOL}]^{VERB}

(A urological surgeon identified that a 13-year-old bi-genital child in Suphanburi must consult a psychiatrist.) (MGR online-01)

(12) thang phaet rongphayaban Lampang^{SAY} **rabu**^{VER} tam bairaprongphaet^{ANG} ok ma [wa mi^{REL} laksana awaiyawaphet kamkuam^{ATT}]^{VERB}

(The Lampang Hospital medical team identified, according to the medical certificate, the presence of ambiguous genitalia.) (Thairath-01)

(13) phaet^{SAY} **winitchai**^{VER} [wa mi^{REL} phawa phetkamkuam^{ATT}]^{VERB}

(The doctor diagnosed the patient with a condition of ambiguous genitalia.) (Ejan-01)

In the example, medical professionals are positioned as sayers in verbal clauses, including “sanlayaphaet thangdoen patsawa” (urological surgeon), “thang phaet rongphayaban Lampang” (Lampang Hospital medical team), and “phaet” (doctor). These clauses project a projected clause within the verbiage. In example (11), the verbal process “rabu” (identified) projects a material clause as verbiage, offering medical guidance on treating ambiguous genitalia. The clause advises that an intersex child consult a psychiatrist, affirming the medical perspective that treatment should address both physical sex characteristics and the child's psychological state to support gender-affirming surgery.

The relational clauses in examples (12) and (13), projected from the verbal process, describe the ambiguous genitalia characteristics of intersex individuals. While these clauses do not explicitly identify a carrier, the context indicates that the attributes refer to intersex individuals. Medical personnel use the term “awaiyawaphet kamkuam” (ambiguous genitalia) to describe variations in sex development. This term implies that intersex genitals do not align with prototypical male or female norms, as they cannot be categorized within typical sexual development. The word “kamkuam” (ambiguous) presupposes the existence of prototypical genitals, a concept broadly accepted without explanation. The experiential meaning of these verbal clauses reflects the medical gaze, which labels intersex individuals as patients and significantly impacts their status in society.

However, the news content lacks specific medical information on the potential health issues these variations might cause. At the same time, the intersex individual in the example appears willing to undergo the physical examination without expressing any reservations. This indicates that both the doctor and the intersex individual share the presupposition that any deviation from typical male or female sexual development is considered abnormal.

3.5. Abnormal bodies

Thai newspapers rarely address intersex variations in the context of health issues, providing little detail on how such conditions affect the body or reproductive system. Instead, they focus on describing the genitals, hormones, or chromosomes of intersex individuals as abnormal and requiring urgent treatment. News coverage does not explore the experiences of intersex individuals beyond their perceived abnormalities and offers no evidence of symptoms that genuinely affect their bodies. This study asserts that variations in sex development among intersex individuals are not medical emergencies but rather emergencies concerning sex assignment and the performance of femininity or masculinity in public spaces. Relational clauses are used in news reports to attribute abnormal characteristics. Thai newspapers engage with the voices of parents to affirm the perceived abnormalities of intersex children and underscore the challenges of raising them within gender norms. This portrayal disconnects intersex variations from issues of bodily autonomy or diversity.

(14) (omitted)^{CAR} **mi**^{REL} nueangok lek lek phlo ok ma^{ATT} chak awaiyawaphetying^{LOC}
(The child has a small tumor protruding from the female genitalia.) (Thairath-01)

The newspaper engages with the mother’s voice to describe abnormalities in the intersex child’s body, using a relational process to convey these characteristics. In example (14), the mother describes the child’s genitalia as abnormal due to a small tumor protruding. The relational process “mi” (has) attributes “nueangok lek lek phlo ok ma” (a small tumor protruding) to the female genitalia of the intersex child. Here, “tumor” refers to an enlarged clitoris, which the mother interprets not as a typical feature but as an abnormal growth. The mother does not rely on medical evidence to identify these characteristics but instead draws on socio-cultural knowledge of normal sexual development within the binary sex system.

Newspapers engage with intersex voices to emphasize that intersex individuals themselves acknowledge their perceived abnormalities. This engagement reinforces the notion of abnormality as a collectively accepted reality. Newspapers draw on medical perspectives to elaborate on these abnormalities, referencing biomedical knowledge of chromosomes and hormones. These narratives legitimize the treatment of intersex children without requiring their consent, further entrenching the concept of abnormality.

(15) (omitted)^{CAR} **roem mi**^{REL} khwamphitpakati^{ATT} tangtae wai thi khuan tong mi
prachamduean^{LOC}
(I began experiencing abnormalities from the age when I should have started
menstruating.) (Khaosod-02)

The relational clause in example (15) reflects the voice of an intersex individual. The relational process “roem mi” (began experiencing) assigns the attribute “khwamphitpakati” (abnormalities) to the carrier, referring to the intersex individual. The abnormality is specified by the circumstantial element of time, “tangtae wai thi khuan tong mi prachamduean” (from the age when I should have started menstruating), indicating the reproductive stage when it first appeared. The experiential meaning of this relational

clause portrays the possession of a negative attribute but does not establish a categorical relationship that defines identity, as variations in sex development are defined within the notion of medical abnormalities rather than self-classifications. Thus, no new gender category has been proposed for intersex individuals.

3.6. Socially problematized bodies

Newspaper coverage examines how sex characteristics become societal concerns when they conflict with socio-cultural understandings of sex and gender. This study found that in Thai society, intersex variations are not seen as medical emergencies but rather as challenges within a system that strictly defines sex categories as male or female because these categories enable individuals to construct identities naturally within the roles of men or women. The findings reveal that Thai newspapers focus more on the social implications of intersex variations than on health issues. Additionally, intersex individuals and their parents may face difficulties in defining identities according to the gender binary. These challenges do not affect physical health but influence psychological and emotional well-being, fostering a sense of inferiority and shaping public expressions of masculinity and femininity.

Newspapers convey these social constraints through relational clauses that describe negative attributes, expressing feelings of social inferiority, while behavioral and material clauses reflect a perceived inability to perform specific actions, thereby contributing to difficulties in social integration.

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(16) dek song phet^{IDED} ko khong tong pen^{REL} pomdoi^{IDR} tit tua^{LOC} pai talot^{EXT}

(A bi-genital child will likely carry an inferiority complex throughout their life.)

(Matichon-02)

Newspapers engage with the voice of the provincial governor to describe a socially constructed sense of inferiority through a relational clause. This dialogue underscores concerns about intersex children and advocates for urgent treatment. In example (16), the relational process “ko khong tong pen” (will likely carry an inferiority complex) links the subject with the attribute, categorizing the child as having an inferiority complex. Circumstantial elements expand the relational process to specify location and duration. The experiential meaning suggests that an intersex child is perceived as having an inferiority complex throughout life unless treated to conform to a typical gender.

Biological sex is central to defining male and female identity in Thai society. Although nature determines physical sex as a biological characteristic, when it does not align with the gender binary, society typically perceives this mismatch as a form of anomaly. The concern of the provincial governor is not centered on the child’s health. Instead, he assumes that if an intersex child grows up in society, the child is likely to develop an inferiority complex due to the prevailing socio-cultural belief that typical gender is rooted in male and female sex. This relationship extends to gender expression, such as attending school, using restrooms, dressing, interacting, presenting gender on official documents, and engaging in other social activities.

The newspaper reported statements from the president of a Thai charitable organization to convey concerns and emphasize the need to assist intersex child. The president’s discussion of the social constraints faced by the child expressed through a behavioral clause with the negative marker “mai,” draws attention to the challenges the child is likely to encounter. The experiential meaning indicates that the intersex child may struggle to integrate into society without establishing a “real” gender identity. In this context, a “real” gender identity is deemed achievable only through gender-affirming surgery to align with male or female norms.

(17) dek^{BEH} mai samat khao sangkhom^{BEHAV}
(The intersex child is unable to socialize in Thai society.) (Daily News-01)

The voice of the president of a charitable organization in example (17) is presented in a behavioral clause. The newspaper engages with this voice to describe the social limitations of an intersex child. The behavior “dek” (child) in the subject position refers to the intersex child, and the behavioral process “mai samat khao sangkhom” (unable to socialize), marked by the negative marker “mai,” conveys these limitations. This depiction underscores the child’s challenges while legitimizing the president’s actions, particularly the financial assistance provided for treatment and surgery. The social difficulties, however, are not caused by the child’s genital structure but by societal norms enforcing gender expression to align with the male-female binary based on biological sex.

4. Discussion

The experiential meaning derived from transitivity analysis supports the hypothesis that Thai newspapers do not actively promote knowledge about bodily diversity. Instead, they represent intersex bodies as existing outside the natural sex binary. The status of knowledge about intersex in Thai society remains deeply entrenched in Cartesian medical paradigms and the gender binary, which categorize variations in sex development as genetic abnormalities.

In Thai society, the absence of knowledge and discourse surrounding intersexuality has led to a lack of recognition of intersex individuals as a distinct category within the spectrum of sex or gender. The normative assumption in Thai society is that “true sex” must correspond to either male or female. This assumption reflects societal conformity to traditional gender expressions. Newspapers, medical professionals, government agencies, charity officers, parents, and even intersex individuals themselves continue to accept medical procedures aimed at normalizing bodies that differ from the typical male and female sexes. The study found no questioning of these procedures or calls for bodily autonomy for intersex children. This evidence aligns with Butler’s (1990, as cited in Secomb, 2017) proposition that gender identity does not exist independently of body and language; Language and cultural practices construct gender and prescribe its repeated performance through the human body.

Thai newspapers do not address challenges related to sexual orientation, heterosexual marriage, health issues, or reproductive problems among intersex individuals. This

absence contrasts with studies in other countries, such as those by Guntram and Zeiler (2016), Henningham (2019), Johnson (2017), and Jones (2016). Instead, the primary focus in the news is the normalization of genital surgery to affirm gender expressions. These expressions include social practices, such as behavior, clothing, or interactions, that signal a person's gender identity as masculine or feminine. Concerns about gender identity align with Jackson's (2004) observation that Thai society emphasizes gender identity through masculine and feminine practices. Therefore, variations in sex development challenge traditional gender norms because biological sex remains central to the construction of gender identity.

Intersex individuals in Thai society face challenges in obtaining legal recognition due to the lack of acknowledgment of bodily autonomy for intersex persons. Legal and bureaucratic systems, rooted in the gender binary, marginalize intersex individuals by enforcing binary categories in areas such as birth registration, identification, school attendance, inheritance, and marriage. These systems leave little room for intersex identities. Roemer (2023) observes that distinct intersex citizenship status is not feasible within a binary society and will require significant time to achieve. Even if implemented, only a few intersex individuals would be able to attain this status due to the complexity and cost of bureaucratic and medical procedures.

This study suggests that the intersex community should collaborate with medical teams and interdisciplinary health professionals to promote knowledge about intersex issues in the education system. Since Thailand's bureaucratic and legal systems prioritize medical knowledge, this implies that social movements related to intersex issues cannot independently establish social practices.

5. Conclusion

Thai newspapers depict intersex bodies outside the natural sex binary, framing them as barriers to gender socialization. These portrayals reflect six distinct characteristics of intersex bodies and suggest that bodies not conforming to the binary system are strange and abnormal. The newspapers engage in dialogue with intersex individuals to convey their perceived strangeness and bodily abnormalities through mental and relational clauses. These individuals are not shown associating their sex development with the construction of an intersex identity. Thai newspapers also reflect the perspectives of medical voices, suggesting that intersex bodies are ambiguous and should, therefore, undergo medical interventions. This perspective is described through verbal and material clauses. Moreover, newspapers often articulate their narratives alongside parents, government agencies, and charity officers in news events, employing verbal and mental clauses to evoke feelings of pity and solicit societal support to raise funds for surgical interventions for impoverished intersex children, particularly for gender-affirming surgeries. In some instances, government agencies are cited expressing societal constraints through behavioral clauses, where these constraints arise not from health or physical abilities but from the challenge of aligning physical sex characteristics with a masculine or feminine identity.

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